

Participant ID	Raw data	Codes	Codes #2 iteration	Concept	Category
E2	Nowadays, if people want to make an appointment at a hospital, it's much easier . The Mobile JKN app allows people – for example BPJS participants – if they are not happy with their currently registered primary care facility, they can easily switch it. Making payments is easy as well.	Easier appointments via mHealth		Administrative and access benefits	Perceived usefulness & engagement patterns of mHealth
E2	Nowadays, if people want to make an appointment at a hospital, it's much easier. The Mobile JKN app allows people – for example BPJS participants – if they are not happy with their currently registered primary care facility, they can easily switch it . Making payments is easy as well.	Easy facility switching via mHealth			
E2	Nowadays, if people want to make an appointment at a hospital, it's much easier. The Mobile JKN app allows people – for example BPJS participants – if they are not happy with their currently registered primary care facility, they can easily switch it. Making payments is easy as well .	Easy payments via mHealth			
E1	As for digital transformation in the health sector, it's certainly been very good. Because after all, since the pandemic, maybe 95% of all stakeholders in health have moved towards digitalisation. It's just that now, since it's no longer a pandemic, awareness of using these health applications has started to decrease. Especially among the public, actually. For healthcare facilities, currently the most use is for booking, scheduling, and teleconsultation, which some young people are still perhaps using. But even that is only for conditions where their health issue is minor and urgent enough that they do a teleconsultation. And also, from the policy side, the Ministry of Health still doesn't have a ministerial regulation for telemedicine or teleconsultation. So at the moment not many hospitals are using teleconsultation or telemedicine.	Healthcare facilities use apps mainly for admin tasks			
E1	Now if all of that (i.e., real-time integration) can be accommodated, then of course it will speed up service. If service is faster, automatically patient satisfaction increases. Because indeed one function of IT is to speed up service and also to improve patient safety.	Service efficiency drives satisfaction			
E1	As for digital transformation in the health sector, it's certainly been very good. Because after all, since the pandemic, maybe 95% of all stakeholders in health have moved towards digitalisation. It's just that now, since it's no longer a pandemic, awareness of using these health applications has started to decrease. Especially among the public, actually. For healthcare facilities, currently the most use is for booking, scheduling, and teleconsultation, which some young people are still perhaps using. But even that is only for conditions where their health issue is minor and urgent enough that they do a teleconsultation. And also, from the policy side, the Ministry of Health still doesn't have a ministerial regulation for telemedicine or teleconsultation. So at the moment not many hospitals are using teleconsultation or telemedicine.		mHealth seen as non-essential	Curative-focused use & low preventive uptake	
E1	Now, essentially the point is how to continuously increase user engagement. Especially for preventive, monitoring, and rehabilitative activities. At present a lot of health app usage is more for curative purposes or treatment only. So people use them only when they need to. Except perhaps for chronic patients who have been identified and need rehabilitation or monitoring. If their caregiver is attentive, they will help the survivor (the patient). But if the caregiver's awareness is lacking, then automatically it's also difficult to input the survivor's health data. Whether the survivor is of cancer, diabetes, or something else—because actually it's quite comprehensive now, every disease has a digital solution; it's just a matter of how it's utilised now.	Apps used mainly for curative needs			
E1	Now, essentially the point is how to continuously increase user engagement. Especially for preventive, monitoring, and rehabilitative activities. At present a lot of health app usage is more for curative purposes or treatment only. So people use them only when they need to. Except perhaps for chronic patients who have been identified and need rehabilitation or monitoring. If their caregiver is attentive, they will help the survivor (the patient). But if the caregiver's awareness is lacking, then automatically it's also difficult to input the survivor's health data. Whether the survivor is of cancer, diabetes, or something else—because actually it's quite comprehensive now, every disease has a digital solution; it's just a matter of how it's utilised now.	Preventive and monitoring use remains low			
E1	We hope that engagement isn't only good during a pandemic or epidemic. We actually want it to be used more for prevention and promotion. However, again, the issue is that preventive and promotive aspects are only effective if the quality of information in the app is good.				
E1	Now, essentially the point is how to continuously increase user engagement. Especially for preventive, monitoring, and rehabilitative activities. At present a lot of health app usage is more for curative purposes or treatment only. So people use them only when they need to. Except perhaps for chronic patients who have been identified and need rehabilitation or monitoring. If their caregiver is attentive, they will help the survivor (the patient). But if the caregiver's awareness is lacking, then automatically it's also difficult to input the survivor's health data. Whether the survivor is of cancer, diabetes, or something else—because actually it's quite comprehensive now, every disease has a digital solution; it's just a matter of how it's utilised now.	Utilisation gap, not technology gap	Utilisation gap despite available solutions		
E2	Because if we talk about digital health, the scope is extremely broad, including health information systems and so on. So perhaps firstly, regarding mobile health, I think it cannot be separated from – number one – the penetration of mobile phones in our country. Second is internet penetration. Then third is the development of all kinds of mobile-based technologies which perhaps were not initially designed for health but later came to be used in health. So I think the development of mobile health here involves aspects related to infrastructure, aspects related to the development of various applications, and aspects related to social factors.	Adoption depends on phone penetration		Socio-demographic and contextual drivers of engagement	
E2	So when people are already using a lot of technology, as more and more people adopt and use it, inevitably people will follow the process of technological development rather than become socially alienated. This is perhaps the macro picture. The micro picture, which is more specific to health, is that its development was triggered because the larger ecosystem was already using mobile technology and the public at large had already experienced it; only then did we in the health sector think about how to utilise it for health functions or purposes.				
E2	Because back then, mobile phones were only used as a tool for telephone communication, and the internet was separate. So the era when people could easily access the internet using their mobile phones, and then the multimedia era, I think became the second generation where the benefits started to be envisioned more in the health sector. And I think in the current era – especially during COVID – it has become very apparent.				
E2	Another aspect [supporting mHealth apps], which I think may not be specific to the medical side, is that we can see the use of mobile phones becoming more and more widespread and even being introduced at increasingly younger ages. This might be related to psychological and mental aspects for our children now. Our children, perhaps from a very young age, don't have a caregiver and instead already have a digital nanny. This carries all sorts of risks.				

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E2	Because back then, mobile phones were only used as a tool for telephone communication, and the internet was separate. So the era when people could easily access the internet using their mobile phones, and then the multimedia era, I think became the second generation where the benefits started to be envisioned more in the health sector. And I think in the current era – especially during COVID – it has become very apparent.	Pandemic-driven usage motivation			
E1	Now, essentially the point is how to continuously increase user engagement. Especially for preventive, monitoring, and rehabilitative activities. At present a lot of health app usage is more for curative purposes or treatment only. So people use them only when they need to. Except perhaps for chronic patients who have been identified and need rehabilitation or monitoring. If their caregiver is attentive, they will help the survivor (the patient). But if the caregiver's awareness is lacking, then automatically it's also difficult to input the survivor's health data. Whether the survivor is of cancer, diabetes, or something else—because actually it's quite comprehensive now, every disease has a digital solution; it's just a matter of how it's utilised now.	Caregiver awareness affects data input			
E2	Now, regarding the public, I think education [regarding data privacy and protection] is needed. And educating people on this isn't easy. The public's views are varied. For example, take an app like Halodoc. Some people feel they benefit from that app being available. Others are worried about using it. Health workers' perceptions are also mixed – there are hospitals that cooperate with Halodoc, and some that do not.	Stakeholder trust heterogeneity affects adoption			
E1	Now one challenge is how to maintain the quality of that health information so that it is continuously updated. The information should be easy to understand, you know. And also the visuals need to be engaging to look at. And since Gen Z now mostly prefer videos, you see—or infographics where they don't have to read a lot of text. So maybe that's the challenge at present. Hopefully that answers it, or if something was missing and needs to be asked again, please go ahead.	Younger users prefer visual formats			
E2	Then if they [developers] create an app that turns out to consume a lot of memory, of course users will not like it. Secondly, people will surely ask – for example, when using an app, since we have limited data quotas – how much data transfer is being sent or used. That also becomes an issue.	Users dislike heavy apps		Lightweight, resource-conscious design	Usability, accessibility & information quality
E2	Generally speaking, I think all of us as app users will certainly feel more satisfied if an app is lightweight.	App size affects user acceptance			
E2	Then if they [developers] create an app that turns out to consume a lot of memory, of course users will not like it. Secondly, people will surely ask – for example, when using an app, since we have limited data quotas – how much data transfer is being sent or used. That also becomes an issue.				
E2	Moreover, if on the other hand the app comes with lots of images, features, videos, and so on that perhaps do not match the users' needs... We know many people do use multimedia devices. But multimedia content is something they wanted from the start. However, if within an app it comes in the form of advertisements that they did not expect and it becomes part of the app – consuming memory, bandwidth, and data – then I think it becomes an issue.				
E2	Moreover, if on the other hand the app comes with lots of images, features, videos, and so on that perhaps do not match the users' needs... We know many people do use multimedia devices. But multimedia content is something they wanted from the start. However, if within an app it comes in the form of advertisements that they did not expect and it becomes part of the app – consuming memory, bandwidth, and data – then I think it becomes an issue.	App features not aligned with user needs	Feature–need mismatch reduces usability	Feature–need alignment and clarity of content	
E2	Now, there are also other revenue sources, such as advertising. But ads naturally come with the drawback of reduced user comfort.	Ads reduce user comfort			
E2	Now, regarding user satisfaction, I agree that the user interface and user experience are key to users feeling happy using a system, including, for example, the speed at which they obtain the information or service they want	UI/UX drives user satisfaction	Good UI/UX boosts user satisfaction		
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E1	Now one challenge is how to maintain the quality of that health information so that it is continuously updated. The information should be easy to understand, you know. And also the visuals need to be engaging to look at. And since Gen Z now mostly prefer videos, you see—or infographics where they don't have to read a lot of text. So maybe that's the challenge at present. Hopefully that answers it, or if something was missing and needs to be asked again, please go ahead.	Info must be easy to understand			
E1	However, again, the issue is that preventive and promotive aspects are only effective if the quality of information in the app is good	Preventive features require high-quality content			
E1	However, again, the issue is that preventive and promotive aspects are only effective if the quality of information in the app is good	Promotive needs good information			
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E2	But what I recall is that when we were on the regulatory sandbox panel, we had a team that evaluated aspects related to the UI and UX of any application involved in the regulatory sandbox. In those evaluations, things were viewed from the user's perspective. So we invited, for example, some elderly people to see how older users perceive the UI/UX – whether, from their perspective, the UI and UX have been considered by the programmers when developing the application. We also invited representatives of people with disabilities. They were asked, for instance, if this application is used by someone with a visual impairment, is there a feature to access the application via audio?	User-inclusive design practices emerging in Indonesia		Inclusive and accessible interface design	
E2	We also invited representatives of people with disabilities. They were asked, for instance, if this application is used by someone with a visual impairment, is there a feature to access the application via audio? So the idea was not to have too many images, but to ensure that key features or menus can be converted from text to voice	Need for audio access for visually impaired users			
E2	I think many studies mention the importance of UI and UX. However, to be honest I do not know if there is any collaboration or initiative between network providers and the technology providers who build the apps – or any government regulation – such that requirements or recommendations are issued that apps must adhere to certain standards. Frankly I'm not sure whether Kominfo (the Ministry of Communication and Information) would regulate things to that extent.	No clear regulation on UI/UX standards			
E2	Back then we had considered such aspects in the regulatory sandbox. But so far, after the regulatory sandbox, it seems UI/UX aspects have not yet been included as specific recommendations – whether in policies on digital health applications, I think they haven't been included – even though it appears there is some discussion about it. But I'm not sure it has shown up in any actual regulation.	UI/UX not included in current digital health policies			
E2	Back then we had considered such aspects in the regulatory sandbox. But so far, after the regulatory sandbox, it seems UI/UX aspects have not yet been included as specific recommendations – whether in policies on digital health applications, I think they haven't been included – even though it appears there is some discussion about it. But I'm not sure it has shown up in any actual regulation.	No formal regulation on usability standards	UI/UX standards not yet regulated		
E2	I think many studies mention the importance of UI and UX. However, to be honest I do not know if there is any collaboration or initiative between network providers and the technology providers who build the apps – or any government regulation – such that requirements or recommendations are issued that apps must adhere to certain standards. Frankly I'm not sure whether Kominfo (the Ministry of Communication and Information) would regulate things to that extent.	No clear regulation on UI/UX standards	Lack of UI/UX regulation		
E1	Usually any estimate also depends on the policy of the facility, looking at each one's historical data, how long the doctor can serve a patient. Because you also can't just say, for example, 10 minutes — for a senior doctor, just uncapping their pen or putting on their stethoscope takes time. That also becomes an issue. So the age factor plays a role as well.	Age affects response time	Doctor age slows response time	Clinical complexity limits response time	Clinical workflow realities & workforce adoption
E1	[Participant]: Wow, that's a complex question. The reason so many hospitals now don't use per-patient time slots for doctors is, as I've observed in public and private hospitals, it's super duper complex — because a doctor's duties, when they're in the clinic, can suddenly include an emergency call from the operating room, an emergency call from the ICU, and of course emergencies are put first.	Multitasking makes scheduling complex			
E1	So that's [i.e., per-patient time slots] the tricky part, because a doctor's work isn't just focused on one thing, like a lecturer's is. A lecturer, if their job is teaching, they just teach, and other things can be handled by someone else. But a doctor's duties are multitasking, so to speak. That's what makes it difficult — it's complex.				
E1	So in the end, when we at Hermina were designing the application initially, we tried using slots — sort of to make it so patients wouldn't wait long. In the end, we just did away with it, because it's really difficult operationally in the field. Not to mention if, say, someone is late — then we have to compensate somehow, whether it's apologising or maybe giving a discount or something. So it just becomes complex.	Managing lateness creates extra workload			
E1	So that's [i.e., per-patient time slots] the tricky part, because a doctor's work isn't just focused on one thing, like a lecturer's is. A lecturer, if their job is teaching, they just teach, and other things can be handled by someone else. But a doctor's duties are multitasking, so to speak. That's what makes it difficult — it's complex.	Fixed scheduling unrealistic			
E1	So this area [i.e., response time] [i.e., response time] is very sensitive, and it's indeed difficult for us to schedule their time. Because sometimes, if a patient is really serious with complications, it's impossible to make their consultation time the same as a patient who just has a cough and cold. I mean, even a cough and cold has its own diagnosis, but say this gentleman has diabetes and hypertension — you can't check him in as short a time.				
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E1	At most, management can give a recommendation — like, if you want to do a consultation with a patient or respond to a patient, how long should it be — and also provide evidence from the transaction logs perhaps. You can see, if they use a hospital information system (SIMRS), what the average duration is for handling a patient in the clinic. And even that can't be made the same across the board. The dental clinic versus the dermatology clinic versus the OB/GYN clinic — those can't be equated. For OB/GYN maybe the doctor has to prepare equipment first; if suddenly some equipment isn't available, they have to call the pharmacy, and so on — it's a hassle. So even just between clinics, for certain types of cases, the ideal recommended time varies.	Consultation duration varies by clinic			
E1	Not to mention the ER — the ER definitely can't be standardised, I think. Now, for inpatient care there is already a set duration. For BPJS (national health insurance) they have a very rigid timeline for the clinical pathway; insurance does as well. But indeed the current issue is mostly in the outpatient clinics: how to ensure patients aren't waiting too long.	Inpatient timelines fixed; outpatient not			
E1	Now if all of that (i.e., real-time integration) can be accommodated, then of course it will speed up service. If service is faster, automatically patient satisfaction increases. Because indeed one function of IT is to speed up service and also to improve patient safety.	Integration speeds service			

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E1	For the back office, the main goal is certainly to speed up service—whether in registration or in payment. Because payment is also linked to registration, especially if using insurance or other third-party providers. Now usually what sometimes takes a while is the verification process, then checking whatever platforms are still there to be able to process the payment. This whole process up to the payment settlement is what can become complex, because if you want to integrate into payments, the front-end integration also has to be sorted out.				
E1	And then there's this, plus political issues as well. Sometimes doctors just can't do it (i.e., setting slot time per patient) — they have to provide services, and then later on they have to meet with management and so on. The thing is, in how the doctor system works, especially since doctors are partners for the facility... Some are employees, some are partners, but most are partners. So their setup is profit-sharing, and that will also affect their remuneration.	Organisational dynamics limit adoption of time slots			
E1	Usually any estimate also depends on the policy of the facility, looking at each one's historical data, how long the doctor can serve a patient. Because you also can't just say, for example, 10 minutes — for a senior doctor, just uncapping their pen or putting on their stethoscope takes time. That also becomes an issue. So the age factor plays a role as well.	Response-time estimates depend on facility policy			
E1	Even for the simplest thing we can think of — setting a slot for one patient and determining the ideal length of service time — it can't be done. I found that there's no formula for that. Especially if it's related to teleconsultation, that is an even lower priority for them. Because, basically, if a teleconsultation patient's safety level is on a scale of 1 to 3, maybe it ranks around 10th in priority. I mean, if a person knows their condition is really severe, an emergency, they will surely go straight to a facility, since there's an intervention that must be done.	Teleconsultation low priority		Teleconsultation deprioritised	
E1	As for digital transformation in the health sector, it's certainly been very good. Because after all, since the pandemic, maybe 95% of all stakeholders in health have moved towards digitalisation. It's just that now, since it's no longer a pandemic, awareness of using these health applications has started to decrease. Especially among the public, actually. For healthcare facilities, currently the most use is for booking, scheduling, and teleconsultation, which some young people are still perhaps using. But even that is only for conditions where their health issue is minor and urgent enough that they do a teleconsultation. And also, from the policy side, the Ministry of Health still doesn't have a ministerial regulation for telemedicine or teleconsultation. So at the moment not many hospitals are using teleconsultation or telemedicine.	Teleconsultation used for mild and urgent cases			
E1	As for digital transformation in the health sector, it's certainly been very good. Because after all, since the pandemic, maybe 95% of all stakeholders in health have moved towards digitalisation. It's just that now, since it's no longer a pandemic, awareness of using these health applications has started to decrease. Especially among the public, actually. For healthcare facilities, currently the most use is for booking, scheduling, and teleconsultation, which some young people are still perhaps using. But even that is only for conditions where their health issue is minor and urgent enough that they do a teleconsultation. And also, from the policy side, the Ministry of Health still doesn't have a ministerial regulation for telemedicine or teleconsultation. So at the moment not many hospitals are using teleconsultation or telemedicine.	Teleconsultation used mainly by younger users			
E1	[Participant]: Oh yes, about the health workers' perspective, do you need that as well? Earlier we were talking from the public (patient) side—I forgot. From the health worker side, the key is internal policy. Because in healthcare it's like in the military, you know. Or the police. If the boss says it must be used, then everyone uses it. Except for doctors who are, quote-unquote, "senior." Those ones perhaps already have lots of patients and other technical obstacles—maybe they also have difficulty in terms of accessing or typing quickly, right. Now, this is also important so that internal regulations mandate that health workers use the application. Because if it's not mandatory—well, trying to manage doctors is more difficult, right, since doctors are usually smarter than us. So if there's no compliance requirement, usually their obedience or adherence is also low.	Voluntary adoption leads to low adherence	Voluntary use leads to poor compliance	Workforce capability & internal policy	
E1	From what I observe, the ones who are patient nowadays are the younger doctors, since they already definitely depend on digital. It's just that, as mentioned, there really should be a compliance requirement. Because otherwise they might go and make their own data backups as well. If there's no compliance and no support, so that's how it is from the health workers' side.	Need for compliance requirements for health workers			
E1	[Participant]: Oh yes, about the health workers' perspective, do you need that as well? Earlier we were talking from the public (patient) side—I forgot. From the health worker side, the key is internal policy. Because in healthcare it's like in the military, you know. Or the police. If the boss says it must be used, then everyone uses it. Except for doctors who are, quote-unquote, "senior." Those ones perhaps already have lots of patients and other technical obstacles—maybe they also have difficulty in terms of accessing or typing quickly, right. Now, this is also important so that internal regulations mandate that health workers use the application. Because if it's not mandatory—well, trying to manage doctors is more difficult, right, since doctors are usually smarter than us. So if there's no compliance requirement, usually their obedience or adherence is also low.	Senior doctors face technical and workload barriers			
E1	[Participant]: Oh yes, about the health workers' perspective, do you need that as well? Earlier we were talking from the public (patient) side—I forgot. From the health worker side, the key is internal policy. Because in healthcare it's like in the military, you know. Or the police. If the boss says it must be used, then everyone uses it. Except for doctors who are, quote-unquote, "senior." Those ones perhaps already have lots of patients and other technical obstacles—maybe they also have difficulty in terms of accessing or typing quickly, right. Now, this is also important so that internal regulations mandate that health workers use the application. Because if it's not mandatory—well, trying to manage doctors is more difficult, right, since doctors are usually smarter than us. So if there's no compliance requirement, usually their obedience or adherence is also low.	Health worker adoption driven by internal policy	Internal policies strongly influence frontline adoption		
E1	[Participant]: Yes, organisational factors are the main determinant indeed—especially in terms of policy. In fact, it starts with the processes as well. And certainly, one thing that usually makes doctors angry is if the IT support isn't responsive, or if there isn't even any IT staff. They're told to use an application but no one can support it. Now, that usually makes them reluctant to use it. And then the system's quality also greatly affects them, especially the quality of information. Moreover, if the patient data is not accurate, you know—that can also make health workers reluctant	Lack of IT support discourages use	App performance tied to available IT support		

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E1	[Participant]: Yes, organisational factors are the main determinant indeed—especially in terms of policy. In fact, it starts with the processes as well. And certainly, one thing that usually makes doctors angry is if the IT support isn't responsive, or if there isn't even any IT staff. They're told to use an application but no one can support it. Now, that usually makes them reluctant to use it. And then the system's quality also greatly affects them, especially the quality of information. Moreover, if the patient data is not accurate, you know—that can also make health workers reluctant	Inaccurate data reduces trust			
E1	So actually the second key point is how we ensure the healthcare facility truly complies [data privacy standard] — meaning it also needs to be ISO certified and so on, have good IT governance, etc. Because security isn't only about the application being secured, but the operations must be guaranteed as well.	Both technical and operational safeguards needed		Security measures build trust	Data privacy, security & user trust
E1	And of course, [security] audits. Sometimes people or organisations forget about audits; they only audit finance, whereas now audits also need to be done on the IT side. Those kinds of things, if all implemented, should be able to provide assurance.	IT audits build assurance			
E1	Then, as mentioned, it (i.e., security) needs to be supported by technical factors as well, and all operations should be clearly defined for how services must be delivered. If someone wants to make a complaint, there should be a clear route for that. And there should be a continuous security campaign too. Hopefully then people will be more confident in digitalisation.	Security requires strong technical support			
E1	Then also, from the technology side, they have secured things properly in terms of the protocols and the network topology. Another important thing is continuous security awareness campaigns that must be carried out by the facility. It's the same as what banks do — they routinely send security campaigns to their customers and also to their staff. At least we create an environment where everyone remains in an alert state, because if we aren't continuously given awareness campaigns, we end up in our comfort zone, just taking it easy, even asleep on the job, and then we don't know when our data gets stolen or whatever. So campaigns are important as well and ideally should be done regularly.	Regular awareness to prevent complacency	Continuous security awareness campaigns		
E1	Then, as mentioned, it (i.e., security) needs to be supported by technical factors as well, and all operations should be clearly defined for how services must be delivered. If someone wants to make a complaint, there should be a clear route for that. And there should be a continuous security campaign too. Hopefully then people will be more confident in digitalisation.				
E1	So actually the second key point is how we ensure the healthcare facility truly complies [data privacy standard] — meaning it also needs to be ISO certified and so on, have good IT governance, etc. Because security isn't only about the application being secured, but the operations must be guaranteed as well.	Facility privacy compliance required			
E1	[Participant]: Actually, when it comes to security issues—whether payments, registration, or consultation—right now the main fear for healthcare facilities is that they must comply with the Personal Data Protection Act. If a facility is already compliant with the PDP law, already ISO 27001 certified, then automatically patients or consumers will trust it more. Because nowadays a lot of people's digital literacy is getting better, especially Gen Z, since soon the main consumers at healthcare facilities will mostly be Gen Z. They already understand how to distinguish which applications are safe and which aren't, including access protocols whether from the web or the mobile health side itself—so that's the key. Basically, as I said, if they are certified to international security standards and they implement good practices—especially if they even win an award from the Ministry of Health (now there is a Digital Maturity Index rating), and have also been assessed by BSSN (the national cyber security agency)—then automatically that can increase the trust of patients or consumers. So essentially for security it comes down to what actions the facility takes to secure the application and especially the users' data privacy.	Standards compliance increases trust			
E1	Secondly, it's along the same lines as the question: how do we trust a mobile banking application? In reality, if there is a trusted seal from VeriSign, for example, or other authorities that conduct comprehensive security assessments or audits — a stamp from ISO 27001, for instance — and the application is already using protocols like SSL or TLS, plus ideally if it can even implement two-factor authentication, then that inspires trust.				
E1	Because what we have to implement is basically the same as in the financial sector for security issues. Sometimes a doctor will say, "If I use an app, my data might get stolen." In that case, that doctor might as well still be keeping their money under the mattress! It's the same thing — financial data is only their transactional data or text data. But if we have ensured that our level of compliance is on par with financial applications, then trust in that application or organisation should no longer be in doubt. Especially if, for example, it is also accredited — supported, say, by having paripurna or unggul accreditation — so it's consistent with the ISO certification they have obtained, and its legality is also proven by that accreditation.				
E1	[Participant]: The Kominfo regulation (Ministry of Communication and Information Regulation) is already very rigid. All application providers dealing with public data, especially health and financial data, are required to register their application with Kominfo (the Ministry of Communication and Information). If not, it's actually illegal. It's just like digital signatures—digital signatures already have ones verified by Kominfo. It's the same with health applications: they must be registered as an Electronic System Provider (PSE).	Health apps must register with government			
E1	So that's the first thing. Nowadays an mHealth app vendor can't just casually provide health services; they must be officially registered with Kominfo.				
E1	Also, actually in Kominfo's regulations it is stated that every application that is registered is required to secure the application and consumer data. But again, the monitoring and evaluation in our country is, well, "extraordinary," quote-unquote.				
E1	Next, about accreditation: as far as I recall, KARS International has also mandated that healthcare facilities must have an application and also ensure the security of their patient data. So if they already use one, ideally if they have passed paripurna (full) accreditation, at minimum that aspect is fulfilled, right. It's like how in universities the highest grade is unggul (excellent); in hospitals it's called paripurna. There is also an international accreditation—we have that as well. But both paripurna and international definitely include criteria for how they must comply, especially as I mentioned in terms of securing data.	Accreditation signals compliance with security standards			
E2	Now, because I mentioned [digital] literacy, it becomes important that if, say, a health facility or the public uses an application, they need to be made aware of their consent regarding that application. When there is an app, of course there's a consent process. To what extent do people pay attention to what's written in that agreement?	Low awareness of consent agreements		User attitudes toward consent & privacy	

Participant ID	Raw data	Codes	Codes #2 iteration	Concept	Category
E2	Now, because I mentioned [digital] literacy, it becomes important that if, say, a health facility or the public uses an application, they need to be made aware of their consent regarding that application. When there is an app, of course there's a consent process. To what extent do people pay attention to what's written in that agreement?	Voluntary data sharing vs fear of misuse			
E2	Now, regarding the public, I think education [regarding data privacy and protection] is needed. And educating people on this isn't easy. The public's views are varied. For example, take an app like Halodoc. Some people feel they benefit from that app being available. Others are worried about using it. Health workers' perceptions are also mixed – there are hospitals that cooperate with Halodoc, and some that do not.	Public needs education on data privacy			
E2	We often, whenever we install an app, just click "next-next-next" until it's done, never reading it. Yet on the other hand, we get upset about personal data protection. So in my opinion that's a bit inconsistent. For example, someone is happy for their data and photos to appear on an app's running leaderboard or photo feed when they go jogging, but at another time they worry that their picture on that feed might be misused by someone else.	Privacy worries despite skipped consent	Users skip consent but still fear misuse		
E1	[Participant]: Actually, when it comes to security issues—whether payments, registration, or consultation—right now the main fear for healthcare facilities is that they must comply with the Personal Data Protection Act. If a facility is already compliant with the PDP law, already ISO 27001 certified, then automatically patients or consumers will trust it more. Because nowadays a lot of people's digital literacy is getting better, especially Gen Z, since soon the main consumers at healthcare facilities will mostly be Gen Z. They already understand how to distinguish which applications are safe and which aren't, including access protocols whether from the web or the mobile health side itself—so that's the key. Basically, as I said, if they are certified to international security standards and they implement good practices—especially if they even win an award from the Ministry of Health (now there is a Digital Maturity Index rating), and have also been assessed by BSSN (the national cyber security agency)—then automatically that can increase the trust of patients or consumers. So essentially for security it comes down to what actions the facility takes to secure the application and especially the users' data privacy.	Younger users have higher security awareness			
E2	However, if someone develops an app and then the app doesn't perform well, in my opinion what needs to be regulated is not how to make them perform or not – that's their own responsibility. What needs to be regulated is the developer's responsibility to the users or subscribers.	Developer accountability to users must be ensured		Accountability in app lifecycle	
E2	For example, someone creates an app, people register, and it collects health data. But then when the app shuts down, are they accountable to the users? For instance, they should inform: "We are closing the app. You still have the right to retrieve your data until a certain date. After that, your data will be deleted from the system and we guarantee your personal data will not be exposed." That sort of thing might need to be arranged.				
E2	Whether an app ends up slow or not, I think it's too much if the Ministry of Health were to regulate something like that. Even Kominfo probably wouldn't regulate to that extent. That will likely be left to each developer. So if a given developer's system does not perform well, they'll suffer the consequences themselves.				
E2	I also agree with what you said earlier about resources on the developer's side. Now, another issue is that very often developers – when they update or make a new version of an app – because they are rushed, they don't have enough time to do proper testing on the application they created.	Developer resource limits			
E2	[Interviewer]: Okay, thank you, [Participant]. I also agree with what you said earlier about resources on the developer's side. Now, another issue is that very often developers – when they update or make a new version of an app – because they are rushed, they don't have enough time to do proper testing on the application they created.	Updates lack proper QA	Updates lack proper testing		
E2	For example, someone creates an app, people register, and it collects health data. But then when the app shuts down, are they accountable to the users? For instance, they should inform: "We are closing the app. You still have the right to retrieve your data until a certain date. After that, your data will be deleted from the system and we guarantee your personal data will not be exposed." That sort of thing might need to be arranged.	Prevent data exposure post-shutdown			
E2	For example, someone creates an app, people register, and it collects health data. But then when the app shuts down, are they accountable to the users? For instance, they should inform: "We are closing the app. You still have the right to retrieve your data until a certain date. After that, your data will be deleted from the system and we guarantee your personal data will not be exposed." That sort of thing might need to be arranged.	Notify users of closure	Apps must notify users before shutdown		
E2	So in my view, the health sector is still cautious about regulating this, even though awareness is quite high and it's been frequently discussed. For example, BPJS Kesehatan already has a Data Protection Officer. They are already referring to the PDP law. They see that every institution that manages personal data must have a DPO, and they also carry out Data Privacy Impact Assessments. The Ministry of Health has done that as well. They understand these requirements, but it seems they haven't assigned who or which unit will serve as the Data Protection Officer. That unit hasn't been formally established, and for instance the practice of performing Data Privacy Impact Assessments hasn't been implemented	Unclear responsibility for data protection tasks			
E1	Also, actually in Kominfo's regulations it is stated that every application that is registered is required to secure the application and consumer data. But again, the monitoring and evaluation in our country is, well, "extraordinary," quote-unquote.	Weak monitoring and evaluation	Security oversight weak and infrequent	Weak enforcement and monitoring	
E1	And then, if the Personal Data Protection law is enforced—like for example the recent breaches of the National Data Centre (PDN) or Satu Sehat, where PeduliLindungi's data was hacked—actually the public could sue the government as well. But in the end, if there are regulations but the execution is not carried out, it's all the same. So the important thing is the implementation of the enforcement itself.				
E1	However, the argument that comes up, again, from organisations is: "We have an internal audit that monitors things." But how good is their internal audit? We had BSSN assess us once — security was only assessed that one time. Now, those kinds of things, there's no ongoing monitoring for either. Usually it's only when a data breach goes viral on social media that the Ministry of Health, BSSN, and so on, finally step in.				
E1	So indeed enforcement and monitoring need to be carried out intensively. But I do feel sorry for our BSSN — it has to oversee so many sectors, yet its manpower is, well, only so much. So I don't really know either, honestly.				

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E2	If we wait through the usual hierarchical process, it may take quite a long time. But if there's a problem related to personal data – a big public commotion about the risk to the public, to doctors, or say, I don't know, a case where a public official's health data is leaked via an app – only then will the regulations be discussed.	Reactive data-governance	Regulation reacts only after crises		
E2	As far as you know, to what extent are mHealth applications in Indonesia concerned with data protection? And what can we do – either from the government's side or the mHealth providers' side – to reassure users that they are sufficiently safe? What approach can be taken? That would be our last question. [Participant]: First, from the regulatory side, we are only halfway there. We have the Personal Data Protection Act (UU PDP), but the implementing Government Regulation (PP) for it hasn't been issued yet. Even if the implementing regulation comes out, technical guidelines for implementing personal data protection in the health sector have not yet emerged.	Regulation needed for data protection			
E2	In my opinion, if we want the health sector to be protected against the various personal data risk factors – breaches and so forth – the relevant regulations or laws really need to be issued first, so that the health sector can prepare.				
E2	What does that tell us? Each party that will choose whether to collaborate or use such an app has its own considerations or views. And as I mentioned, the regulatory reference is not completely clear on this, so people aren't confident	Lack of regulatory clarity hinders trust		Gaps and ambiguity in regulation	
E2	Various technologies have indeed developed extensively, but the legal aspect remains a challenge. This includes, for example, issues related to the use of mobile technology by the public that are not specifically health-related – for instance, issues of misinformation or hoaxes related to health information delivered via mobile. This is also an issue that I consider important, because nowadays people use mobile phones and we are in various WhatsApp groups. But then the information that comes through – information, for example in my field of health – frankly, false information about things like anti-vaccine messages and so on also spread	Legal aspects lag behind technological growth			
E2	But the detailed framework hasn't been well elaborated. The legal aspects haven't been well elaborated either. So, I think this remains an issue.	Legal aspects unclear			
E2	Up to and including now, for example, the use of AI that is embedded into mobile health. So I think the technological development is amazingly diverse and its uses are also diverse. The challenge is the clarity of the legal aspects. This, I think, is still an issue.	Lack of legal clarity			
E2	So this is still tied – the law is in place, and the Government Regulation hasn't come out yet. I think once the PP is issued, it will coincide with the establishment of a Personal Data Protection Commission or Agency that will handle disputes if there are parties who hold, process, or use personal data improperly or illegally. Parties who misuse data could then face sanctions and so on.	Implementing regulation not yet issued			
E2	So this is still tied – the law is in place, and the Government Regulation hasn't come out yet. I think once the PP is issued, it will coincide with the establishment of a Personal Data Protection Commission or Agency that will handle disputes if there are parties who hold, process, or use personal data improperly or illegally. Parties who misuse data could then face sanctions and so on.				
E2	Now, since the PP hasn't been issued, the health sector also hasn't made any specific guidelines. In fact, if the health sector wanted to create specific guidelines, it could, because there are examples from other countries to draw from. But I think if a specific regulation were made while the higher-level regulation isn't out yet, our colleagues at the Ministry of Health would likely say, "Why prepare sector-specific data protection rules? The Data Protection Act and its PP aren't fully settled, the draft Ministry of Health regulations aren't finished – why should we prepare data protection regulations specific to the health sector when those responsible haven't even issued the technical rules yet?" – meaning Kominfo.				
E2	Now, at the Ministry of Health level it hasn't been done, let alone further down – in hospitals and so on. And this comes down to resources. A Data Protection Officer, for example, could be a third party rather than an internal person at a health facility. But these provisions haven't been issued yet.				
E2	And then, if the Personal Data Protection law is enforced—like for example the recent breaches of the National Data Centre (PDN) or Satu Sehat, where PeduliLindungi's data was hacked—actually the public could sue the government as well. But in the end, if there are regulations but the execution is not carried out, it's all the same. So the important thing is the implementation of the enforcement itself.				
E1	As for digital transformation in the health sector, it's certainly been very good. Because after all, since the pandemic, maybe 95% of all stakeholders in health have moved towards digitalisation. It's just that now, since it's no longer a pandemic, awareness of using these health applications has started to decrease. Especially among the public, actually. For healthcare facilities, currently the most use is for booking, scheduling, and teleconsultation, which some young people are still perhaps using. But even that is only for conditions where their health issue is minor and urgent enough that they do a teleconsultation. And also, from the policy side, the Ministry of Health still doesn't have a ministerial regulation for telemedicine or teleconsultation. So at the moment not many hospitals are using teleconsultation or telemedicine.	Telehealth adoption constrained by regulatory gaps	Lack of telemedicine regulation	Multi-stakeholder misalignment and conflicting incentives	Governance, regulation & ecosystem alignment
E2	It reached the point that the government created a regulatory sandbox. Take, for example, the Halodoc application. Halodoc – even though it passed the regulatory sandbox – is still not clearly defined in our regulatory framework. What do we even call this service? The new Health Act does mention telehealth that is direct-to-consumer. Previously, our regulations only talked about telemedicine between health facilities. Now, in the Health Act it has begun to mention telehealth from the community to providers.	Unclear status of direct-to-consumer telehealth			
E1	[Participant]: Certainly the Ministry of Health must put in place comprehensive compliance measures, especially since teleconsultation already has a few providers but there's no truly solid legal regulation yet.	MoH must enforce compliance measures			
E2	So yes, this goes back to the development of mobile health. Mobile health, in my view, is also part of building a collective consensus. So when that consensus hasn't been established by the Ministry of Health, we end up waiting – perhaps if there's something viral related to Halodoc or others, only then might the Ministry of Health create a regulation.	mHealth development requires multi-stakeholder alignment			
E1	So perhaps the recommendation would indeed come from the facility's policy side, but also taking into account track history, then what the health workers' demographics are like, their age range, as well as the disease trends. The hope is that if a facility already has good evidence-based, data-driven decision making, then perhaps something like that could be done. Yeah, maybe something like that.	Data-driven mHealth policy			
E2	I know a few hospitals use services – for example, for delivering medicine after a patient receives care and a prescription at the hospital – and those delivery services partner with third parties, including Halodoc and others. But some say this is risky. So in the end it comes back to each party's decision.	Outsourced medication delivery			

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E2	What would be the impact if, say, real-time integration between the BPJS application, the health facilities, and the hospitals involved could be achieved in the near future? What would be the effect, [Participant]? And would it be possible, considering how many health facilities we have and the complexity of patient issues in the field? [Participant]: If we're talking about technology – is it possible? Yes, I think it's possible. The next question is whether it would succeed or not. That's a separate question. If the question is whether it's possible, I'd say yes, it's feasible. The second point is how it could potentially be realised. I suspect, firstly, that the latest user numbers are actually quite high for a mobile application – in terms of the number of subscribers worldwide, in my opinion. At least if we look at various other apps. Perhaps those with larger user bases are apps in China or India. As far as I know – I forget the name of the one in India, if I'm not mistaken – that had quite a large user count as well. Mobile JKN, I believe, is already quite large.	High user volume strengthens integration readiness		Integration feasibility depends on resources	Integration, infrastructure & business sustainability
E2	I can only imagine – BPJS has a choice to make. Let's say they choose to increase the number of users, which would have to be followed by providing adequate resources for BPJS's IT systems. So if, for instance, they push to increase users but don't provide the resources, it will just result in things running slowly.	Growth without scaling harms performance			
E2	So I think it comes back to that second point: whether there are resources or not. And secondly, if the resources are there, whether they are used to support the system's performance or not. If the question is "Is it (i.e., real-time integration) possible or not?" – yes, it's possible. But perhaps, as mentioned, issues of resources and the regulatory framework need attention.	Integration depends on resource availability			
E2	If the question is "Is it (i.e., real-time integration) possible or not?" – yes, it's possible. But perhaps, as mentioned, issues of resources and the regulatory framework need attention.				
E1	The issue that usually arises is actually when the patient uses insurance, because private insurance in Indonesia is very complex. It doesn't have an aggregator, or even if there is a major aggregator, it's quite difficult technically to integrate it. Now, if they pay out-of-pocket, that means it has to integrate with various channels as well—for cash, debit, credit cards, and so on.				
E1	Certainly, in terms of satisfaction—from my research, patients will be satisfied if it's end-to-end integrated. But again, it depends on the strength of the IT resources that the facility has. And usually if there's an API, it means there must be legal personnel, partnerships as well involved there, finance people too, and you also have to ensure that the channels being integrated truly have value for the facility.				
E2	Because if we talk about digital health, the scope is extremely broad, including health information systems and so on. So perhaps firstly, regarding mobile health, I think it cannot be separated from – number one – the penetration of mobile phones in our country. Second is internet penetration. Then third is the development of all kinds of mobile-based technologies which perhaps were not initially designed for health but later came to be used in health. So I think the development of mobile health here involves aspects related to infrastructure, aspects related to the development of various applications, and aspects related to social factors.	Internet access affects mHealth use			
E2	Because back then, mobile phones were only used as a tool for telephone communication, and the internet was separate. So the era when people could easily access the internet using their mobile phones, and then the multimedia era, I think became the second generation where the benefits started to be envisioned more in the health sector. And I think in the current era – especially during COVID – it has become very apparent.				
E2	Because if we talk about digital health, the scope is extremely broad, including health information systems and so on. So perhaps firstly, regarding mobile health, I think it cannot be separated from – number one – the penetration of mobile phones in our country. Second is internet penetration. Then third is the development of all kinds of mobile-based technologies which perhaps were not initially designed for health but later came to be used in health. So I think the development of mobile health here involves aspects related to infrastructure, aspects related to the development of various applications, and aspects related to social factors.	Infrastructure shapes adoption			
E2	If the question is "Is it (i.e., real-time integration) possible or not?" – yes, it's possible. But perhaps, as mentioned, issues of resources and the regulatory framework need attention.	Integration needs strong business processes			
E1	Certainly, in terms of satisfaction—from my research, patients will be satisfied if it's end-to-end integrated. But again, it depends on the strength of the IT resources that the facility has. And usually if there's an API, it means there must be legal personnel, partnerships as well involved there, finance people too, and you also have to ensure that the channels being integrated truly have value for the facility.				
E1	So, again it (i.e., real-time integration) comes back to business processes. If, for instance, a facility has a business process owner and good business process management, then other related subprocesses should also be integrated. Because indeed the key to the success of digitising health applications is how they can form an integrated digital ecosystem. That's the key point.				
E2	What would be the impact if, say, real-time integration between the BPJS application, the health facilities, and the hospitals involved could be achieved in the near future? What would be the effect, [Participant]? And would it be possible, considering how many health facilities we have and the complexity of patient issues in the field? [Participant]: If we're talking about technology – is it possible? Yes, I think it's possible. The next question is whether it would succeed or not. That's a separate question. If the question is whether it's possible, I'd say yes, it's feasible. The second point is how it could potentially be realised. I suspect, firstly, that the latest user numbers are actually quite high for a mobile application – in terms of the number of subscribers worldwide, in my opinion. At least if we look at various other apps. Perhaps those with larger user bases are apps in China or India. As far as I know – I forget the name of the one in India, if I'm not mistaken – that had quite a large user count as well. Mobile JKN, I believe, is already quite large.	Success uncertain despite feasibility			
E1	So, for example, our recommendations in this area include automation for refunds, then verification for transparency, and flexibility in payment methods. If these recommendations were implemented, would that be possible, [Participant]? How realistic is it if we introduce such improvements in the payment aspect for each mHealth application? [Participant]: In this context it comes down to integration, right, because the healthcare ecosystem is complex. Essentially it means integrating with the payment ecosystem. Because when we talk about payments, patients can pay out-of-pocket, they can use private insurance, and also BPJS (the national insurance), right. Now, if it's BPJS, then of course it has to be integrated into every hospital because that has clear compliance requirements.	Payment integration requires compliance		Interoperability challenges	

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E2	So perhaps the key is interoperability. This is probably a big task for us. For example, right now the lack of interoperability is quite extreme. So, say there are various apps or commercial applications that are not connected to each other. E-commerce applications and Google, or others, are not linked to each other either. These are things that might need to be discussed. This is still a challenge that likely needs to be overcome.	Interoperability is a major challenge			
E2	So, say there are various apps or commercial applications that are not connected to each other. E-commerce applications and Google, or others, are not linked to each other either. These are things that might need to be discussed. This is still a challenge that likely needs to be overcome.				
E1	The issue that usually arises is actually when the patient uses insurance, because private insurance in Indonesia is very complex. It doesn't have an aggregator, or even if there is a major aggregator, it's quite difficult technically to integrate it. Now, if they pay out-of-pocket, that means it has to integrate with various channels as well—for cash, debit, credit cards, and so on.				
E2	It's just that I think there are a few things that probably need harmonisation. For example, many hospitals in Indonesia have also developed applications for their own hospitals. However, the challenge is that hospitals face constraints from the JKN system.	National metrics restrict local innovation			
E2	If a JKN patient registers at a hospital not through Mobile JKN, the hospital's performance is considered not so good. This is an issue, in my view, because then the hospital cannot really make use of or promote their own application.				
E2	I know a few hospitals use services – for example, for delivering medicine after a patient receives care and a prescription at the hospital – and those delivery services partner with third parties, including Halodoc and others. But some say this is risky. So in the end it comes back to each party's decision.	Third-party risk concerns	Concerns over external service integration		
E2	[Participant]: I think this relates to the character or business model of the app developer. If we talk about the sustainability of an innovation, and the source of revenue is how many users the app has, that usage is usually converted into value. A certain number of app users will correspond to the value of that app.	App value measured by number of users		Business models constraints	
E2	If they can show that their app is being used by a lot of people, I think that becomes the first thing – probably their priority when talking about their innovation's growth.				
E2	[Participant]: This reminds me of when I participated in the regulatory sandbox. If I'm not mistaken, one or two participants in the first mHealth regulatory sandbox – when we later did the monitoring and evaluation, their app was no longer around. Either it had shut down, for example, or the app was sold and then merged with another app. So, if we use a market perspective – especially nowadays with the economy being difficult – indeed there is a tendency for some people to develop an app not with the intention of a very long-term venture. They develop an app, launch it successfully, get a certain number of subscribers, and the goal really is to sell it, not to grow it further.	Short-term app development motives	Build-to-sell business model		
E2	So, if we use a market perspective – especially nowadays with the economy being difficult – indeed there is a tendency for some people to develop an app not with the intention of a very long-term venture. They develop an app, launch it successfully, get a certain number of subscribers, and the goal really is to sell it, not to grow it further. Yes, I read that there are some entrepreneurs whose model is like that: from an innovation to an app, then sell it for profit, and afterwards they'll create other apps. I think that is also part of the market's characteristics – some players want to operate that way.				
E2	Another possible model, I think, is that users who download the app don't necessarily contribute money to the company. They are converted into statistics. Perhaps through a subscription model – so some users then subscribe, for example – that can be converted into revenue. It can also take the form of other partnerships.	Partnerships as alternative revenue source	Partnership-based revenue model		
E2	I think forms of partnership could avoid using ads. For example, having an offline network: if the app partners with healthcare facilities, then if a healthcare facility uses the application, the app company could receive a commission or give a discount, for instance. That could be one key way to gain revenue from users.				
E2	Another possible model, I think, is that users who download the app don't necessarily contribute money to the company. They are converted into statistics. Perhaps through a subscription model – so some users then subscribe, for example – that can be converted into revenue. It can also take the form of other partnerships.	Subscription model as revenue option			